

CERTIFICATE

OF APRECIATION

SHARQ FALSAFASI

Ko'bayeva Surayyo Askarali kizi

THE ADULTS AS ENGLISH LEARNERS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

